

Low-dose combination of Rho kinase and L-type Ca(2+) channel antagonists for selective inhibition of depolarization-induced sustained arterial contraction.

Cristina Porras-González¹, Patricia González-Rodríguez¹, Eva Calderón-Sánchez²,

José López-Barneo¹ and Juan Ureña¹

1. Instituto de Biomedicina de Sevilla (IBiS), Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío/CSIC/Universidad de Sevilla, Dpto. de Fisiología Médica y Biofísica. Avenida Manuel Siurot s/n, E-41013, Seville, Spain

2. Instituto de Biomedicina de Sevilla (IBiS), Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocío/CSIC/Universidad de Sevilla, Seville, Spain

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Nifedipine (PubChem CID: 4485) Fasudil (PubChem CID: 3547) Verapamil (PubChem CID: 62969) abstract

L-type Ca²⁺ channels (LTCCs) are involved in the maintenance of tonic arterial contractions and regulate the RhoA/Rho-associated kinase (ROCK) sensitization cascade. We have tested effects of individual and combined low concentrations of LTCCs and ROCK inhibitors to produce arterial relaxation without the adverse side effects of LTCCs antagonists. We have also studied whether this pharmacological strategy alters Ca²⁺-dependent electrical properties of isolated arterial and cardiac myocytes as well as cardiac contractility. Rat basilar, human carotid and coronary arterial rings were mounted on a small-vessel myograph to measure isometric tension and cardiac contractility was measured in Langendorff-perfused rat heart. Simultaneous cytosolic Ca²⁺ concentration and arterial diameter were measured in intact pressurized arteries loaded with Fura-2. Patch-clamp techniques were used to measure electrical properties in isolated cardiac and arterial myocytes. Low concentrations of LTCCs and ROCK inhibitors reduced the tonic component of moderate depolarization-evoked contraction, leaving the

30 phasic component practically unaltered. This selective vasorelaxant effect was more
31 marked when the LTCCs and ROCK inhibitors were applied together. In the concentration
32 range used (nM), Ca²⁺ currents in arterial myocytes, cardiac action potentials and heart
33 contractility were unaffected by this pharmacological approach. In conclusion, low doses
34 of LTCCs and ROCK inhibitors could be used to selectively relax precontracted arteries in
35 pathologic conditions such as hypertension, and cerebral or coronary spasms with minor
36 side effects on physiological contractile properties of vascular and cardiac myocytes.

37 **1. Introduction**

38 Several highly prevalent pathologic conditions, such as hypertension and coronary or
39 cerebral arterial spasms are accompanied by tonic arterial contractions, which are
40 mediated, at least in part, by transmembrane Ca²⁺ influx through L-type voltage-
41 dependent Ca²⁺ channels (LTCCs) in vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMCs). Although
42 LTCCs blockers are commonly used in the clinical setting to induce arterial relaxation,
43 these agents can also produce undesirable adverse effects due, among other causes, to
44 their inhibitory action on heart beat frequency and contraction (Hofer et al., 1993; Furberg
45 et al., 1995; Abernethy and Schwartz, 1999). Therefore, new therapeutic approaches,
46 based on recent advances in the understanding of the mechanisms of VSMCs reactivity,
47 should be investigated to optimize the treatment of vasospasms.

48 In this regard, previous studies in our laboratory have suggested a double functional role
49 for LTCCs in VSMCs. In addition to their classical ionotropic function necessary for rapid,
50 or phasic, VSMC contraction, LTCCs are involved in the maintenance of protracted, or
51 tonic, arterial contractions through the metabotropic Ca²⁺ release from internal stores and
52 regulation of the RhoA/Rho-associated kinase (ROCK) sensitization cascade (
53 Fernández-Tenorio et al., 2010; Fernández-Tenorio et al., 2011). The RhoA/ROCK
54 pathway participates in the pathogenesis of major vascular disorders (Loirand et al., 2006
55) and can be activated by membrane depolarization (Fernández-Tenorio et al., 2011; Mita
56 et al., 2002; Sakurada et al., 2003). In line with these findings, fasudil, a selective ROCK
57 inhibitor with safety profile in patients, has demonstrated efficacy in stable effort angina,
58 vasospastic angina and cerebral vasospasm (Masumoto et al., 2002; Shibuya et
59 al., Contents lists available at ScienceDirect journal homepage:
60 www.elsevier.com/locate/ejphar European Journal of Pharmacology.

61 Based on these data, we hypothesized that combination of ROCK inhibitors and low
62 concentrations of nifedipine and verapamil, two LTCCs inhibitors that differ in their
63 selectivity towards vascular versus cardiac activity, could be a safe and ef ficacious
64 therapeutic strategy to treat arterial vasospasm without affecting functions that depend on
65 fast LTCC activation. Herein, we show that individual and simultaneous application of low
66 doses of LTCC antagonists and fasudil reduces depolarization-evoked tonic arterial
67 contractions without side effects on normal Ca₂p-dependent electrical properties of
68 vascular and cardiac myocytes and cardiac contractility.

69 **2. Materials and methods**

70 **2.1. Samples and ethics approval**

71 Human coronary arterial rings were obtained from 3 patientssubjected to orthotopic heart
72 transplantation that had suffered heart failure owing to dilated cardiomyopathy of ischemic
73 origin (stages II –IV of the New York Heart Association). Human carotid arterial rings were
74 obtained from 3 donor patien ts. Experimentation with human tissues was approved by
75 the local Ethics Committee on Human Research of the University Hospital “Virgen del
76 Rocío ”(HUVR) of Seville. The study was done in agreement with the standards of the
77 2008 revision of the declaration of Helsinki. Rat basilar arterial rings and hearts were
78 obtained from Wistar rats (n¼32) and cardiac ventricular myocytes were obtained from
79 neonates Wistar rats (n¼19). All experiments were conducted in accordance with the
80 Spanish legislation on protection of animals (Royal Decree 53/2013), conformed to the
81 Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament,and approved by the local animal care
82 committee (Comité Ético de Experimentación de la Universidad de Sevilla).

83 **2.2. Preparation of arterial rings and measurement of arterial contractility**

84 Adult male Wistar rats (250 –300 g) were killed by intraperitoneal administration of an
85 overdose of sodium thiopental (120 mg/kg). The brain was removed into cold Hank's
86 solution and the basilar artery was dissected out and cleaned of adherent meninges. Rat
87 and human arteries were cut in rings (/C242 mm) and mounted on a small-vessel
88 myograph (Danish Myo Technology, Aarhus, Denmark) to measure tension, connected to
89 a digital recorder (AcqKnowledge 3.8.1; Biopac System Inc., Goleta, CA, USA). The rings
90 were placed on a chamber filled with Krebs's solution, bubbled with 95% O₂and 5% CO₂
91 at pH 7.4. Special care has been taken to use in our experiments arterial rings with

92 similar length, diameter and localization. Before the experiments, segments were
93 subjected to an optimal tension (90% of tension equivalent to an intramural pressure of
94 100 mmHg) and stabilized for at least 30 min. After the equilibration period, we discarded
95 arterial rings that developed a tension of >0.1 mN in response to 30 mM KCl (30 K). All the
96 drugs used were added directly to the chamber while vessel tension was monitored.
97 Analysis of the vasorelaxant effect of LTCCs and ROCK inhibitors was done when the
98 inhibitory effect on arterial ring contraction was stabilized. Experiments were performed at
99 30 °C in basilar arterial rings and at 37 °C in human arteries.

100 **2.3. Simultaneous measurement of intracellular $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ and arterial diameter**

101 Experiments were performed as previously described (Calderón-Sánchez et al., 2009).
102 Briefly basilar arteries (12 –14 mm) were incubated in Hank's containing fura-2 AM 1.4
103 μ M for 1 h at room temperature. Arteries were cannulated at each end in a temperature-
104 controlled perfusion chamber (Living Systems Instrumentation), pressurized to 60 mmHg,
105 and perfused with standard Krebs's solution (5 ml/min; 30 °C or 40 °C) to allow
106 stabilization. An optical-based measuring system (Myocam, IonOptix Corporation),
107 coupled to an inverted microscope (Axiovert 35 Zeiss) equipped by epi fluorescence, was
108 used for combined monitoring of Ca^{2+} concentration and outer arterial diameter.
109 $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ was monitored by the 340/380 ratio of the fluorescence intensities measured at
110 510 nm. Fluorescence was background-corrected. Arterial diameter and $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ signals
111 were digitized at 2 Hz and analyzed using IonWizard edge-detection software (IonOptix
112 Corporation). Experiments were performed at 30 °C.

113 **2.4. Ex vivo Langendorff-perfused rat heart**

114 Measurements of heart contractility were done using Langendorff-perfused system. Adult
115 male Wistar rats (250 –300 g) were anaesthetized by intraperitoneal administration of
116 Ketamine/Xilacine (80 mg ketamine hydrochloric acid plus 10 mg of xilacine/kg of animal
117 weight). The hearts were quickly removed, mounted on the aortic cannula of the
118 Langendorff perfusion system apparatus and perfused with an oxygenated Krebs's solution
119 as described previously (Calderón-Sánchez et al., 2009). To obtain an isovolumetrically
120 beating preparation, a latex balloon filled with water and connected by a catheter to a
121 transducer (Abbott, IR) was inserted through the left atrium into the left ventricle and in-
122 flated to provide an end-diastolic pressure between 8 and 12 mmHg. Before each
123 experimental protocol was initiated, the isolated hearts were set at a mean arterial

124 pressure of 60–80 mmHg and were allowed to stabilize at 37 °C for 40 min. Chart Powerlab
125 software (AD Instruments) was used for continuous recording throughout the experiments
126 of heart rate, and maximum positive and negative derivative of left ventricular pressure (dP/dt).
127 The heart contractility under different treatments was evaluated, in rate-paced
128 hearts, by the analysis of dP/dt , which corresponds to % increase of dP/dt normalized to
129 basal dP/dt after stabilization period. The different treatments were administered by a
130 syringe pump (Vial Medical Program 2 Becton Dickinson).

131 **2.5. Preparation of vascular and cardiac dispersed myocytes and patch clamp** 132 **recordings**

133 Basilar artery was placed in 3 ml of cold enzyme cocktail containing collagenase (Sigma
134 type IA, 725 units/ml), elastase (Sigma type III, 0.5 mg/ml), and bovine serum albumin
135 (Sigma Fraction V, 2.5 mg/ml) in isolation buffer. This was kept at 4 °C to depress enzyme
136 activity and to allow the enzymes to diffuse into the extracellular matrix of the tissue. After
137 4 h at 4 °C the enzyme cocktail was warmed in a water bath to 37 °C for 5–10 min to
138 activate the enzymes. The tissue was then removed into fresh isolation buffer and gently
139 triturated until cells could be observed. Isolated cells were placed on coverslips and
140 maintained in isolation buffer. Voltage-clamp recordings in vascular myocytes were
141 performed using the whole-cell configuration of the patch-clamp technique. Ca^{2+} currents
142 were recorded with an EPC-7 amplifier, digitized at a sample interval of 20 ms (10 ms test
143 pulse) or 40 ms (500 ms test pulse) by using A-D interface LIH 1600 (HEKA). Cardiac
144 ventricular myocytes were prepared from 1- to 3-day-old animals and cultured
145 as previously described (Akao et al., 2001). Action potentials were recorded from
146 individual myocytes using the current clamp whole-cell configuration of the patch clamp
147 technique using an EPC-10 UBS patch clamp amplifier (Heka Elektronik). 131 pulses (100
148 pA and 5–10 ms duration) potentials. Data were filtered at 10 kHz, digitized at a sampling
149 interval of 20 μ s and stored on a Macintosh computer. Off-line analysis of data was
150 performed using Igor6. Patch electrodes

151 (2.5–4 M Ω) were pulled from hematocrit capillary glass (Hirschmann Laborgerate; 1.5–
152 1.6 mm OD), fire-polished on a MF-830 microforge (Narishige). All experiments
153 were performed at room temperature (22 °C)

154 **2.6. Solutions, drugs and chemicals**

155 The composition of Hank's solution was (in mM): NaCl 125, KCl 5.36, NaHCO₃ 35, Na
156 2HPO₄ 40.34, KH₂PO₄ 4.44, glucose 10, sucrose 1.45, Hepes 10, pH 7.4. In arterial
157 experiments, the recording chamber was continuously superfused with a standard Kreb's
158 solution (in mM): NaCl 119, KCl 4.7, KH₂PO₄ 41.17, NaHCO₃ 324, CaCl₂ 22.5, MgSO₄
159 41.17, glucose 5.5. 30 mM K⁺ solution was obtained by replacing 30 mM of NaCl with KCl.
160 Vascular smooth muscle cells were obtained in isolation buffer (in mM): NaCl 125, KCl
161 5.36, CaCl₂ 20.16, MgCl₂ 22, NaHCO₃ 35, NaH₂PO₄ 40.34, KH₂PO₄ 4.44, glucose 10,
162 sucrose 1.45, Hepes 10, pH 7.4. In voltage-clamp experiments in isolated basilar
163 myocytes, cells were maintained in physiological salt solution containing (in mM) NaCl
164 137, KCl 5.4, MgCl₂ 21, CaCl₂ 21.8, glucose 10, Hepes 10, pH 7.4. After seal formation the
165 cell was perfused by an external solution containing (in mM) NaCl 130, KCl 5.4, BaCl₂ 21
166 0, glucose 10, Hepes 10, pH 7.4. The internal solution have the following
167 composition (in mM): CsCl 130, MgCl₂ 21, EGTA 5, glucose 10, Na₂-ATP 2, Na-GTP 0.5,
168 Hepes 10, pH 7.2. For whole cell current clamp recordings in cardiac myocytes, the
169 standard bath solution contained (in mM) NaCl 140, KCl 5, MgCl₂ 22, CaCl₂ 22, Hepes 15,
170 glucose 25, pH 7.4. The pipette solution contained (in mM) KCl 140, MgCl₂ 21, Hepes 10,
171 phosphocreatine 5, EGTA 1, Na₂-ATP 4, pH 7.2. Nifedipine (1,4-dihydro-2,6-dimethyl-4-
172 [2-nitrophenyl]-3,5-pyridinedicarboxylic acid dimethyl ester) and verapamil (5-[N-(3,4-
173 Dimethoxyphenylethyl)methylamino]-2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-2-isopropylvaleronitrile
174 hydrochloride) were used as LTCC blockers. Fasudil (1-(5-Isoquinoliny)sulfonyl
175)homopiperazine dihydrochloride) was used as selective ROCK inhibitor. All enzymes and
176 drugs were purchased from Sigma, UK.

177

178 Fig. 1. Effect of fasudil on depolarization-induced contraction in rat basilar arterial rings.
 179 (A, B) Low concentrations of fasudil (0.5 mM) selectively reduce the tonic component of
 180 depolarization-evoked contraction ($n=5$), and higher concentrations (2 mM) also reduce
 181 the phasic component ($n=6$). (C, D) Changes of cytosolic $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ (represented as
 182 fluorescence ratio, F_{340}/F_{380}) and vessel diameter measured in intact pressurized
 183 arteries depolarized with high K_p . Fasudil (10 mM) had no effect on cytoplasmic Ca^{2+} but
 184 increased the arterial diameter. The arrow indicates that although Ca^{2+} concentration was
 185 not affected by fasudil, the ROCK inhibitor inhibited the tonic component of arterial
 186 contraction ($n=3$). Values are presented as mean \pm S.E.M.

187 2.7. Statistical analysis

188 Data are expressed as mean \pm standard error (S.E.M.). Statistical significance was
189 estimated with the paired or unpaired Student's t-test. Repeated-measures ANOVA test
190 was used to compare more than two paired data. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered
191 significant.

192 **3. Results**

193 **3.1. Individual and combined low doses of Rho kinase and L-type**

194 Ca^{2+} channel antagonists selectively inhibit depolarization-induced sustained arterial
195 contraction. We have previously described that depolarization-elicited sustained arterial
196 contraction is mediated by activation of LTCCs and RhoA/ROCK sensitization pathway (
197 Fernández-Tenorio et al., 2011). So, we have studied the effect of individual and combined
198 low concentrations of LTCCs and ROCK inhibitors on the phasic and tonic components of
199 arterial contraction. We have used 30 mM K^+ to shift the membrane resting potential to a
200 moderate level of depolarization ($-24/-34$ mV). This protocol has been applied in
201 numerous laboratories to induce a sustained arterial depolarization that mimics
202 pathophysiological vasospasms (Pesic et al., 2004; Koide et al., 2011). Fig. 1 A shows
203 isometric high K^+ (30 mM)-evoked contractions in a rat basilar arterial ring with a first
204 (phasic) component of 4.95 \pm 0.25 mN peak value and a second (tonic) component with a
205 maximal tension of 7 \pm 0.3 mN (determined at 10 min, $n = 28$) (Fernández-Tenorio et al.,
206 2011). At low concentrations (0.5 mM) fasudil selectively reduced the tonic component
207 although at higher concentrations (2 mM) the two components were affected (Fig. 1 A
208 and B). Simultaneous measurements of myocyte Ca^{2+} concentration and arterial diameter
209 demonstrated that the vasorelaxant effect of fasudil was independent of changes in
210 cytosolic Ca^{2+} concentration (Fig. 1 C and D). Qualitatively similar effects on the tonic
211 component of contraction have been described in previous papers of our laboratory when
212 ROCK was inhibited with Y27632 (Fernández-Tenorio et al., 2011). To study the role of
213 LTCCs on the tonic component of depolarization-evoked contraction, we have tested the
214 vasorelaxant effect of low concentrations of nifedipine and verapamil, two LTCCs
215 antagonists that differ in their relative selectivity towards

216

217 Fig. 2. Effects of low doses of L-type Ca²⁺ channel inhibitors on depolarization-induced
 218 contraction in rat basilar arterial rings. (A, B) Low concentration of nifedipine (2 nM)
 219 selectively reduced the tonic component of depolarization-evoked contraction (n=3),
 220 whereas higher concentrations (8 nM) also reduced the phasic component (n=4). (C, D)
 221 Low concentration of verapamil (5 nM) selectively reduced the tonic component of
 222 depolarization-evoked contraction (n=6), whereas higher concentrations (500 nM) also
 223 reduced the phasic component (n=4). Values are presented as mean
 224 \pm S.E.M. nPo0.05, nnPo0.01, nnnPo0.001.

225

226 Fig. 3. Effects of individual and simultaneous exposure to low doses of L-type Ca²⁺
227 channel and Rho kinase inhibitors on depolarization-induced contraction in rat basilar
228 arterial rings. Low concentration of fasudil (0.25 mM), that selectively reduces tonic
229 component of depolarization-evoked contraction, potentiates the vasorelaxant effect
230 induced by verapamil (10 nM) (n=8). Values are presented as mean S.E.M.

231 vascular versus cardiac activity (Abernethy and Schwartz, 1999). Low doses of nifedipine
232 (2 nM) or verapamil (5 nM) reduced selectively the sustained component of 30K-evoked
233 contractions, although at higher concentrations both nifedipine (8 nM) and verapamil (500
234 nM) inhibited the two components (Fig. 2). The selective vasorelaxant effect of LTCCs
235 and ROCK antagonists was also present when arterial rings were treated simultaneously
236 with low concentrations of fasudil and verapamil. Fig. 3 shows that the selective inhibition
237 of verapamil (10 nM) on the sustained component of depolarization-evoked contraction
238 was potentiated when low concentration of fasudil (0.25 mM) was present. To test the
239 effect of combined application of low doses of fasudil plus a LTCC antagonist (verapamil
240 or nifedipine) we used the protocol indicated in Fig. 4 in which we obtained a cumulative
241 dose-dependent curve of the effect of Ca²⁺channel and ROCK antagonists on the tonic
242 component of depolarization-induced contraction. Fig. 5 shows that at a fixed
243 concentration of fasudil (0.25 mM), lower than that necessary to inhibit the phasic
244 contractions (see Fig. 1 A and B), half of K-induced arterial tonic contraction was obtained
245 with 22.2 nM and 1.59 nM of verapamil and nifedipine respec-

246 tively. Therefore, fasudil potentiates the effects of verapamil and nifedipine applied in the
247 nM range, concentrations at which they have no effects on the phasic component of the
248 arterial contractions. These data indicate that combination of fasudil and LTCC.

249

250 Fig. 4. Effect of fasudil and L-type Ca²⁺ channels' inhibitors on the tonic component of
 251 depolarization-evoked contractions in rat basilar arterial rings. Cumulative vasorelaxant
 252 effect (A) and dose response curve (B) of fasudil on the tonic component of 30K-evoked
 253 contraction (IC₅₀ 0.76 μM, n=43). Cumulative vasorelaxant effect (C) and dose response
 254 curve (D) of verapamil on the tonic component of 30K-evoked contraction (IC₅₀ 43.5
 255 nM, n=47). Cumulative vasorelaxant effect (E) and dose response curve (F) of nifedipine

256 on the tonic component of 30K-evoked contraction ($IC_{50} \frac{1}{4} 2.56$ nM, $n \frac{1}{4} 21$). Values are
 257 presented as mean S.E.M.

258 antagonists results in a powerful inhibitory effect on the sustained arterial tone at
 259 concentrations minimizing the undesirable cardiovascular effects of higher doses of the
 260 drugs.

261

262 Fig. 5. Fasudil potentiates the vasorelaxant effect of LTCCs inhibitors on sustained
 263 component of depolarization-induced contraction. (A) Cumulative vasorelaxant effect of
 264 verapamil in the presence of fasudil (0.25 μM). (B) Cumulative dose-response curves of
 265 individual and combined low doses of fasudil (0.25 μM) and verapamil ($IC_{50} \frac{1}{4} 43.5$ nM
 266 verapamil, $n \frac{1}{4} 7$, $IC_{50} \frac{1}{4} 22.2$ nM, verapamil+fasudil, $n \frac{1}{4} 7$). (C) Cumulative vasorelaxant
 267 effect of nifedipine in the presence of fasudil (0.25 μM). (D) Cumulative dose-response
 268 curves of individual and combined low doses of fasudil (0.25 μM) and nifedipine ($IC_{50} \frac{1}{4}$
 269 2.56 nM nifedipine, $n \frac{1}{4} 21$; $IC_{50} \frac{1}{4} 1.59$ nM, nifedipine+fasudil, $n \frac{1}{4} 19$). Values are
 270 presented as mean \pm S.E.M. $^*P < 0.05$, $^{**}P < 0.01$, $^{***}P < 0.001$.

271

272 Fig. 6. Effect of combined low doses of ROCK plus LTCCs antagonists
 273 on the electrical properties in vascular and cardiac myocytes. (A) Lack
 274 of effect on Ca^{2p} currents in voltage-clamped basilar myocytes treated
 275 with low nifedipine concentration, Nif (L, 3 nM) plus fasudil and reduction
 276 of $Ca^{2 p}$ currents in myocytes bathed with high nifedipine concentration,
 277 Nif (H, 100 nM). (B) Current amplitude (I_m , measured at the end of
 278 depolarizing pulses) as a function of the membrane potential (V_m).
 279 Control, $n \frac{1}{4} 8$; Nif (H), $n \frac{1}{4} 3$; Nif (L) pfasudil, $n \frac{1}{4} 8$. Each point is the
 280 mean \pm S.E.M. Stimulus duration 10 ms. (C) Lack of effect on $Ca^{2 p}$
 281 currents in voltage-clamped basilar myocytes treated with low nifedipine
 282 concentration, Nif (L, 3 nM) plus fasudil ($n \frac{1}{4} 7$) and reduction of $Ca^{2 p}$

283 currents in myocytes bathed with high nifedipine concentration, Nif (H,
284 100 nM) ($n = 4$). Stimulus duration: 500 ms. (D) Statistical analysis that
285 represents maximal Ca^{2+} current (peak) and Ca^{2+} currents at the end
286 of the pulse (Stationary I_{Ca}). Each point is the mean \pm S.E.M. $^*P < 0.05$.
287 (E) Lack of effect of low nifedipine concentration (L, 3 nM) plus fasudil
288 on cardiac action potentials ($n = 5$). Action potential amplitude and
289 duration were reduced with high nifedipine concentration (H, 100 nM)
290 plus fasudil ($n = 5$). (F) Lack of effect of low verapamil concentration (L,
291 5 nM) plus fasudil on action potential ($n = 4$). Action potential amplitude
292 and duration were reduced with high verapamil concentration (H, 100
293 nM) plus fasudil ($n = 3$). Fasudil concentration $\frac{1}{4}$ 1 μ M.

294

295 **3.2. Ca^{2+} -dependent electrical activity in arterial and cardiac myocytes remains** 296 **unaltered with simultaneous exposure to low doses of LTCCs and ROCK inhibitors**

297 As Ca^{2+} channels participate in action potential generation in vascular and cardiac
298 myocytes, we have tested whether the combined pharmacological approach (ROCK
299 inhibitor plus LTCC antagonist) alters myocytes' electrical activity. Voltage-clamped rat
300 arterial basilar myocytes showed characteristic depolarization activated inward currents
301 with a tail at the end of the pulse (Fig. 6 A). These currents had a typical time course and
302 voltage dependence of those mediated by voltage-gated Ca^{2+} channels in VSM cells (
303 Fernández-Tenorio et al., 2010). Application of nifedipine at low concentration (L, 3 nM)
304 plus fasudil (1 μ M) had no effect on Ca^{2+} currents elicited by short- (Fig. 6 A and B) or
305 long-lasting depolarization (Fig. 6 C and D), which were inhibited when nifedipine
306 concentration was increased to 100 nM (H) (Fig. 6 A–D). Action potentials evoked by
307 current injection in dissociated current-clamped rat cardiac myocytes were also unaffected
308 by either 1 μ M fasudil plus 3 nM nifedipine (L, Fig. 6 E) or 1 μ M fasudil plus 5 nM verapamil
309 (L, Fig. 6 F). At higher concentrations, the LTCC antagonists markedly reduced action
310 potential amplitude and duration (H, Fig. 6 E and F). These experiments indicate that
311 simultaneous application of fasudil and LTCC antagonists, in the concentration range at
312 which they selectively inhibit the tonic component of arterial contractions, has no effect on
313 fast transmembrane Ca^{2+} currents in VSMCs or on cardiac action potential waveform.

314 **3.3. Contractility in Langerdoff-perfused hearts remains unaltered**

351

352 **3.4. Low doses of fasudil and nifedipine reduce depolarization-evoked sustained**
353 **contraction in human carotid and coronary arteries**

354 Fig. 8 shows that, as in the rat basilar artery, low doses of fasudil potentiated the
355 vasorelaxant effect of low doses of nifedipine in human carotid (Fig. 8 A–C) and coronary
356 (Fig. 8 D) arterial rings. Nifedipine concentrations at which fasudil (0.25 μ M in carotid and
357 1 μ M in coronary arteries) significantly potentiated the vasorelaxant effects of the Ca
358 $^{2+}$ antagonist were 10 nM and 3 nM for the human carotid and coronary arteries,
359 respectively.

360

361 Fig. 8. Effects of individual and simultaneous exposure to low doses of nifedipine and
362 fasudil on depolarization-induced arterial contraction in human arteries. (A–C)
363 Vasorelaxing effect of nifedipine alone and nifedipine combined with fasudil (0.25 μ M) on
364 30K-induced contraction in human carotid arterial rings. (IC_{50} $\frac{1}{4}$ 2.21 nM, n $\frac{1}{4}$ 6, nifedipine;
365 IC_{50} $\frac{1}{4}$ 1.5 nM, n $\frac{1}{4}$ 7, nifedipine+fasudil). (D) Cumulative vasorelaxant dose-response
366 curve of nifedipine alone and in the presence of fasudil (1 μ M) on 30K- induced contraction

367 in human coronary arterial rings. (IC_{50} $\frac{1}{4}$ 2.85 nM, n $\frac{1}{4}$ 5, nifedipine; IC_{50} $\frac{1}{4}$ 0.84 nM, n $\frac{1}{4}$
368 3, nifedipine+fasudil). Values are presented as mean \pm S.E.M.

369 $nP < 0.05$, $^{nn}P < 0.01$.

370 **4. Discussion**

371 We have previously reported that during sustained depolarizations LTCCs can activate a
372 metabotropic pathway that leads to Ca^{2+} release from intracellular stores and
373 RhoA/ROCK activation, a mechanism that favors sustained arterial contractions with
374 relatively small transmembrane Ca^{2+} influx (Fernández-Tenorio et al., 2011). Based on
375 these data we proposed that simultaneous application of LTCCs and ROCK inhibitors at
376 low concentrations could have potential clinical applicability to antagonize tonic arterial
377 contraction (Abernethy and Schwartz, 1999; Zhao et al., 2011; Vicari et al., 2005)
378 minimizing undesirable adverse effects of higher doses of LTCCs blockers. In this work
379 we have tested the vasorelaxant effect of low doses of fasudil alone or in combination with
380 nifedipine or verapamil, two LTCCs inhibitors that differ in their relative selectivity towards
381 vascular versus cardiac activity (Abernethy and Schwartz, 1999). Our results indicate that
382 either LTCCs or ROCK inhibitors at concentrations lower than those known to exist in
383 plasma during the standard clinical treatments (Shibuya et al., 2005; Cremers et al., 1997;
384 Renwick et al., 1988) can inhibit the tonic component of moderate depolarization-evoked
385 contractions, leaving the phasic component practically unaltered.

386 In agreement with previous results, (Sun and Triggle, 1995) we show that nifedipine is
387 more potent (i.e. effective at lower concentration) as a vasodilating agent than verapamil.
388 Moreover, our data indicate that simultaneous application of LTCC antagonists and fasudil
389 at doses below those necessary to reduce the phasic component of depolarization-
390 induced arterial contraction results in a powerful inhibitory effect on the sustained arterial
391 tone. As LTCCs are also present in vascular and cardiac myocytes,

392 we have tested whether this combined pharmacological approach alters myocytes'
393 electrical activity. Interestingly, we show that low doses of LTCCs plus fasudil, in the range
394 that selectively relaxes tonic contractions in arterial rings, have no effect on action
395 potentials and Ca^{2+} currents, responsible for the phasic, rapid transmembrane Ca^{2+} influx
396 leading to cardiac and vascular myocyte contraction. In agreement with the
397 electrophysiological data the same pharmacological treatment (low dose of verapamil plus

398 fasudil) had no effects on cardiac contractility whereas verapamil at high concentration
399 showed the characteristic of negative inotropic action (Schwinger et al., 1990). Under
400 physiological conditions, cardiac and vascular myocytes generate spontaneous or evoked
401 action potentials that induce short (~ 100 ms) membrane depolarization, Ca^{2+} influx through
402 LTCCs and transient myocyte contraction (Gokina et al., 1996). In contrast, in
403 pathophysiological processes such as hypertension or subarach-noid hemorrhage (Koide
404 et al., 2011; Pesic et al., 2004), VSMCs are permanently depolarized and contracted. It
405 is precisely during sustained membrane depolarizations, a condition that keeps Ca^{2+}
406 channels predominantly in an inactivated state, when they are particularly sensitive to
407 LTCCs inhibitors (Fernández-Tenorio et al.,

408 2011).

409 **5. Conclusion**

410 Although future pharmacological experiments should be done to study in further detail the
411 effects of ROCK and LTCCs inhibitors, we show that low-dose combination of both
412 antagonists could be a potential therapeutic strategy against pathological arterial spasms,
413 with minor side effects on physiological fast, depolarization-evoked, cardiac and vascular
414 contractions.

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